

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ECONOMY OF SURKHANDARO REGION

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Annotation. It is known that small business and private entrepreneurship has a strong place in the experience of world countries with its high results and successes, and in most countries its share in the gross domestic product is 60-70 percent. The development of small business is aimed at creating favorable conditions for economic vitality and an effective competitive environment, stimulating demand by expanding the consumer sector, filling the consumer market with goods and services, protecting the environment, and expanding budget serves. Accordingly, many developed countries strive to fully support small business activities.

Key words: Economy, small business entities, micro-firms, investment, foreign investment, joint venture with foreign capital, innovation, legal and regulatory documents.

INTRODUCTION As a result of the measures implemented in our country to support this direction and create all the necessary conditions, the share of small business entities in the gross domestic product is increasing. If we dwell on specific numbers, 3,804 new small enterprises and micro-enterprises (without farmers and peasant farms) were established in Surkhandarya region in January-December 2023, which is 24.8% less than in the same period last year. means In terms of types of economic activity, the largest number of small enterprises and micro-enterprises are in trade (43.9%), industry (16.1%), agriculture, forestry and fishing (10.8%), construction (6.8 %) in accommodation and food (7.9 %) and transportation and storage (2.5 %).

The 29th goal of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 is to create conditions for the establishment of entrepreneurial activities and the formation of a permanent source of income, to increase the share of entrepreneurship in GDP to 80% and the share of exports to 60%. Issues such as opening 200 new industrial zones in the regions and developing the business incubator system,

supporting entrepreneurship in the regions, and reducing unemployment and poverty have been separately defined.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Shodibekova D.A., Boltaboyev M.R., Kasimova M.S., Ergashkhodjayeva Sh.J., Goyibnazarov B.K., Samadov A.N., Khodjayev from the economists of our republic about the role and importance of small business and entrepreneurship in the development of the national economy and small business management. such scientists conducted scientific research.

Table 1

The main indicators of small business in Surkhandarya region in January-December

	Unit of measure	2022-y.	2023-y.	The difference (+;-)
Number of operating small enterprises and micro-firms	unit	27368	20589	-6779
Number of newly established small enterprises and micro-enterprises	unit	4083	3804	-279
<i>Shares of small business:</i>				
GNP	%	76,1	75,9	- 0,2
Industry	%	42,4	47,3	+ 4,9
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	%	96,1	94,1	- 2,0
Investment	%	49,5	57,9	+ 8,4

Construction	%	92,2	91,3	- 0,9
Retail trade	%	96,6	97,2	+ 0,6
Services	%	64,5	64,4	- 0,1
Shipping	%	84,0	93,4	+ 9,4
Cargo turnover	%	88,7	95,3	+ 6,6
Passenger transportation	%	97,7	97,7	0,0
Passenger traffic	%	98,3	98,6	+ 0,3
Export	%	64,0	72,4	+ 8,4
Import	%	72,6	88,2	+ 15,6

Small business can be seen as an industry that gives new strength and energy to the economy. Newly established enterprises to a certain extent collect and implement the demand, the latest technological innovations and achievements. Accordingly, the level of renewal of enterprises is a unique indicator.

Table 2

Newly established small enterprises and micro-firms in the region, together

	January- December 2022	January- December 2023	Difference (+;-)
Surxondaryo region	4083	3804	-279
cities:			
Termez c.	677	698	+21
regions:			
Angar	226	189	-37
Bandikhan	150	104	-46
Boysun	225	135	-90
Denov	467	425	-42
Jarkurgan	316	293	-23
Kumkurgan	270	195	-75
Kyziriq	160	242	+82
Muzrabot	205	168	-37

Altinsoy	184	249	+65
Sariosiyo	219	212	-7
Termiz	189	166	-23
Uzun	183	150	-33
Sherabad	352	337	-15
Shorchi	260	241	-19

In the months of January-December 2023, the largest number of newly established small enterprises and micro-firms by district are Termiz city - 698, Denov district - 425, Sherabad district - 337, Zharkurgan district - 293, Altinsoy district - 249, Kyziriq district - 242, Shorchi district - 241 and Sariosiyo - 212. The lowest rate was Muzrabot district - 168, Uzun district - 150, Boysun district - 135 and Bandikhon district - 104.

Table 3

Newly established small enterprises and micro-enterprises by types of economic activity, together

	2022 January-December	2023 January- December	Difference (+;-)
All	4083	3804	-279
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	820	411	-409
Industry	678	611	-67
Construction	310	260	-50
Trade	1479	1666	+187
Transport and storage	112	97	-15
Accommodation and food services	253	299	+46
Information and communication	66	108	+42
Providing health care and social services	58	58	+/-
Other activities	307	294	-13

In January-December 2023, the highest number of small business entities per 1000 inhabitants by region is 19.0 units in Termiz district, 18.9 units in Termiz city, 10.7

units in Boysun district, 10.4 units in Bandikhon district, it was 10.0 units in Sherabad district, 9.0 units in Altinsoy district, and 8.9 units in Angor district. In Kumkurgan district, this indicator was the lowest and corresponded to 7.2 units.

Diagram 1

The number of small business entities operating in the regions in January-December 2023 (per 1,000 inhabitants, in units. Small enterprises and micro-enterprises (including farms and peasant farms))

The number of small business entities operating in January-December 2023 was 9.5 units per 1000 inhabitants, while in 2022 this figure was 12.6 units and decreased by 3.1 units compared to 2022. .

In January-December 2023, the share of small entrepreneurship (business) in industry - 47.3%, in agriculture, forestry and fishing - 94.1%, in construction - 91.3%, in investment - 57%, 9%, trade - 97.2%, services - 64.4%, export - 72.4% and import - 88.2%

In January-December 2023, the share of small business in GDP was 75.9%. (76.1% in January-December 2022). The decrease in the share of GNI compared to the previous year is expressed by the increase in the volume of added value in large business entities.

By regions, the highest share of the industrial sector is Bandikhon (100.0%), Boysun (96.2%), Muzrabot (90.1%), Altinsoy (86.8%) and Shorchi (64.6%) districts. constitutes Angor (100.0 %), Boysun (100.0 %), Denov (100.0 %), Muzrabot (100.0 %), Termiz (100.0 %), Sherabad (100.0 %), Shorchi (100.0%), Altinsoy (100.0%) and Uzun (100.0%) districts. In the field of services, Bandikhon (83.5%), Muzrabot (79.8%), Boysun (79.5%), Altinsoy (78.6%), Kyziriq (78.5%) and Uzun (76.3%) districts constitutes Sherabad (98.4 %), Muzrabot (91.0 %), Kyziriq (88.3 %), Bandikhon (87.1 %), Angor (86.7 %), Altinsoy (83.0 %) and Kumkurgan (82.6%) districts.

Diagram 2

Volume and growth rate of construction works performed in small enterprises (businesses) by region in January-December 2023

In terms of regions, the largest amount of construction works performed by small business entities is the city of Termiz (1,835.9 billion soums), Denov (729.9 billion soums), Zhargorgon (514.9 billion soums). m), Boysun (473.6 billion soums), Sariosia (465.5 billion soums), Termiz (423.7 billion soums), Sherabad (377.0 billion soums)), Angor (318.3 billion soums) and Muzrabot (300.8 billion soums) districts.

CONCLUSION

According to the results of the IV quarter of 2023, selective observations were conducted among small enterprises and micro-firms. 1,053 small enterprises and

micro-enterprises participated in this survey. The share of small enterprises and micro-enterprises participating in the monitoring by types of economic activity is in trade - 40.9% (431), in services - 27.5% (290), in construction - 13.6% (143), in industry - 11.5% (121), in agriculture, forestry and fisheries - 6.5% (68).

According to the results of the observation of small enterprises and micro-firms conducted in the IV quarter of 2023, the largest share of enterprises that assessed the economic situation as favorable in the current period by types of economic activity was 38.0% in industry, 37.2% in service, 34.1% in trade and 33.6% in construction. Also, the largest share of enterprises that assessed the economic situation as satisfactory was 80.9% in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, 58.0% in trade, and 57.3% in services.

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